

COMPARISON BETWEEN SIMULATED CENTRAL SUPPORT TESTS AND TWO-SPAN PANEL TESTS FOR SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

Although the static system of sandwich panels for building construction is often a multi-span beam, very little research has been done in the structural behaviour at mid support. As a result, conservative models partly rule the design and according to EN 14509 full-scale tests, denoted as simulated central support tests, are mandatory to determine the local resistance. Considering the mid support the uncertainties affect both the serviceability limit state (SLS) and the ultimate limit state (ULS).

In this paper, the comparison between simulated central support tests and test results on two-span panels for positive support reactions are presented for the SLS. Sandwich panels with 80 mm depth of core and polyurethane foam as core material were chosen. The full scale tests cover wall and roof panels, two support widths (60 and 200 mm), three different spans for simulated central support tests (1000/1100, 2500 and 5900 mm) and one span for the two-span panel tests (2 x 2950 mm). Both, a wider mid support and a lower ratio of sandwich moment to (simulated) mid support reaction positively influenced the wrinkling stress. The simulated central support tests reproduced the first failure mode of two span tests fairly well. Depending on the span EN 14509 over- or underestimates the wrinkling strength. Besides the wrinkling failure, some panels failed in shear or in compression of the core. Both failure modes should not have occurred since the utilisation according to EN 14509 was in each case less than 100 %. This lack of safety may be partly justified due to the fact that the corresponding spans were too small in comparison to real conditions. Nevertheless, it calls the current design practice of EN 14509 into question.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels for building construction usually consist of a light core of polyurethane foam (PUR) or mineral wool and two thin face sheets of steel. They are used as building envelope (wall or roof) with the advantage that they are structural member and thermal insulation altogether. Since the production and the erection are very cost effective, sandwich panels are very popular for industrial, storage and production buildings. The faces normally consist of thin steel plates. Thicknesses vary between 0.4 and 1.0 mm, though face sheets thicker than 0.75 mm are not very common. The inner faces are typically as thick as the outer faces or thinner than the outer faces. If the latter applies, the difference makes about 0.05 to 0.13 mm. Face sheets are flat, lightly profiled or profiled. Flat face sheets show minor load bearing capacity and are vulnerable for visible unevenness. They are thus not so popular under architects, engineers and building owners. Roof panels consist of one lightly profiled and one profiled face sheet, whereas for wall panels both face sheets are normally flat or lightly profiled. The most important core material is PUR. Its density ranges from 36 to 42 kg/m³, its thickness usually from 30 to 200 mm. EN 14509 [1] rules how to test and how to design sandwich panels.

The static system of sandwich panels are mostly multi-span beams in Germany. Kurpiela [2] asked the German sandwich producers in 2010 about the static system of the wall panels mounted between 2008 and 2010. Only 20 % of all panels were installed as single-span beams. This survey does not include data for roof panels, but it can be assumed that the part of multi-span beams is the same or even higher considering the spans of typical industrial roof constructions. In spite of the preferred

multi-span usage the testing and design methods given by EN 14509 incorporate some critical issues concerning the mid support. In ULS the static system is still conservatively reduced to a sequence of single-span beams. In SLS the positive impact of a wide mid support on reducing the moment and increasing the resistance has not been adopted yet. Additionally and most important, the test series for the CE marking according to EN 14509 still incorporates simulated central support tests to experimentally determine the resistance at an intermediate support. In these tests it is common that the span is defined dependent on the core thickness although EN 14509 does not directly demand it. Practically, the element length is 4 to 5 m for core thicknesses up to 60 mm, 5 to 6 m for 80 to 100 mm and 6 to 7 m for 120 mm and more.

This paper concentrates on the resistance obtained out of the simulated central support tests and the comparison of these tests with the corresponding two-span tests. The support width (for the simulated central support and the two-span tests) and the span (only for the simulated central support tests) are varied to demonstrate the influence on the wrinkling stress. Both, wall panels and roof panels were tested. Panels with 80 mm depth of core and PUR as core material were chosen. For all tests only positive mid support reactions were considered which means that the mid support is always under pressure.

2 PREVIOUS RESEARCH AND MID-SUPPORT SPECIFICATIONS IN EN 14509

2.1 Previous research at mid support

In the middle of the 1990s Hassinen and Martikainen [3] undertook a large test series on continuous sandwich panels. Because of the favoured usage in Finland they concentrated on wall panels with mineral wool as core material. At about the same time Berner [4] examined the same problem for sandwich panels with PUR core in Germany. He focused on the evaluation of various simulated central support tests. His test series included only one two-span-test with a support width of 240 mm. The depth of the face sheet's profile was 3.60 mm which is not common any more. Unfortunately, he did not include a corresponding simulated central support test. The test results of both research projects are also summarised in [5]. Meyer [6] derived in his PhD-Thesis a semi-analytical¹ model for the determination of the wrinkling stress. He verified his model on single span and simulated central support tests, but did not consider two-span tests at all. Another semi-analytical² derivation for flat face sheets was developed as part of the PhD-Thesis of Lübke [7]. His numerical and analytical studies are based on simulated central support tests with a span of 960 mm. There is no variation in span, but in support width ($L_s = 10$ and 60 mm). In the scope of work package 2 of the easie project (*Ensuring Advancement in Sandwich Construction through Innovation and Exploitation*) two-span panel tests were conducted to examine the concept of proofing sandwich panels through "design by testing" instead of through the common way "design by calculation" [e.g. 8, 9]. Because of this specialised interest no simulated central support tests were included. And again all wall panels [8] had flat face sheets. The two-span tests in Helsinki [9] were performed on panels with profiled face sheets, but only included two tests with positive mid support reaction. In total it can be concluded that tests on two-span-panels are very rare, especially for roof panels. Every introduced research project or test series contains some disadvantages. It is outstanding that two span tests on roof panels in comparison with simulated central support tests do not exist at all.

2.2 Support reaction capacity

The support reaction capacity is given in EN 14509, E.4.3.2. Equation (1) is valid for mid supports. As illustrated in figure 1 it is assumed that the load spreads linear with a slope of $1/k$ until the middle of the static height e . For foam cores such as PUR k equals 0.5 and e is limited to 100 mm. Alternatively, the support reaction capacity can be conservatively reduced to the contact surface area,

¹ The model is only semi-analytical because Meyer specified factors for the load transfer which are numerically derived.

² The model is only semi-analytical because Lübke specified a variable coefficient for the load distribution which is calibrated on his test results.

so that the support reaction capacity is given by equation (2). Lange and Berner [10], for example, apply equation (2) in their design examples.

$$F_{R2} = B \cdot (L_S + k \cdot e) \cdot f_{Cc} \quad (1)$$

$$F_{R2} = B \cdot L_S \cdot f_{Cc} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Spreading of load at mid support. *Left:* According to EN 14509 for support reaction capacity. *Right:* Conservative assumption. According to EN 14509 for simulated central support test.

2.3 Interaction between bending moment and support force (simulated central support test)

At an internal support the bending capacity of a sandwich panel, namely the wrinkling stress, is reduced due to the support reaction R . The result of this interaction is simulated by a three-point-bending test. Under real conditions a sandwich panel is loaded by temperature difference ΔT , wind (w) and snow (s) loads. If only positive support reactions are considered, the wind pressure on roofs can often be neglected so that wall panels are loaded by ΔT and w and roof panels by ΔT and s . Since the temperature difference mostly leads to higher moments at internal supports, the moment distribution resembles the one given in figure 2. A simulated central support test is able to cause the same ratio between bending moment and support reaction if the span is determined appropriately. Yet, the moment distribution resembles only approximately.

Figure 2: Load as well as moment distribution of a two-span panel and the corresponding simulated central support test

The testing procedure to determine the interaction between bending moment and the support force is regulated in EN 14509, A.7. The span of the test is indirectly specified and “shall be sufficient to ensure that” (EN 14509, A.7.4 [1]) a compressive failure of the core is excluded. For this purpose the simulated support reaction shall be less than F_{R2} according to equation (2) during the test. EN 14509, A.7.4, Note 1 [1] states the reason: “This ensures that all failure modes (wrinkling of the face, compressive failure of the core [...]) are designed for approximately equal levels of safety.” And Note 2 [1] the consequence: “If the test is carried out on a shorter specimen than that described, the failure mode is likely to be dominated by core crushing and a conservative value of the wrinkling stress will be obtained.” As already mentioned in section 1, this leads to element lengths between 4 and 7 m dependent on the core thickness.

This approach implies two questionable assumptions: Firstly, the determination of the failure mechanisms (wrinkling of the face and compressive failure of the core) can be separated if the span of the simulated central support test is long enough. In this case the two failure mechanisms do not interact with each other. Secondly, the additional imperfection due to the mid support reaction is

independent of its extent as long as core crushing is excluded. This somehow contradicts the actual purpose of the test which is to determine the interaction between bending moment and support force.

2.4 Proof of shear resistance

The design of sandwich panels is divided into the SLS and the ULS. In the SLS the analysis is elastic and for multi-span systems plastic analysis is normally used in the ULS. At every intermediate support a plastic hinge with zero bending resistance is assumed for the plastic analysis. This presumes that the first failure mode is wrinkling at mid support. EN 14509 actually requires that shear failure of the core is not the first failure mode (compare EN 14509, E.7.2.1 [1]). To preserve the core from such a shear failure it would make sense to proof the shear resistance on a continuous static system with safety factors according to the ULS. But in practice, the proof of shear resistance is divided into the SLS with a continuous static system and the ULS with a series of single-span panels as static system (compare [10]).

3 TEST PROGRAMME AND TEST SET-UP

3.1 Test programme

One major goal of the test programme was to determine the influence of the span and the support width of simulated central support tests on the wrinkling stress. Furthermore, it was of interest if the simulated central support tests are able to simulate real two-span conditions. Two support widths were chosen: 60 and 200 mm. EN 14509 specifies the support width of 60 mm to simulate the flange width of cold formed steel sections. The support width of 200 mm represents hot rolled steel sections, timber profiles or concrete substructures. Three different spans for simulated central support tests were examined: 5900 mm, 2500 mm and 1000/1100 mm. The longest span equals the span according to EN 14509³. The ratio of (sandwich) moment to support reaction are approximately the same for the shortest span and the two-span tests. The third span of 2500 mm provides further results in between. The span of 2 x 2950 mm for the two span tests formed the maximum span for the element length at hand. For comparison the same panels were tested in six-point-bending to obtain the undisturbed wrinkling stress. All elements and specimen smaller than 6 m were cut out of undamaged parts of tested elements to reduce the amount of testing material. That means that only the elements with 5900 mm respectively 2 x 2950 mm were brand new, all other tests were recycled out of these ones. In total 45 tests on complete panels were conducted. They are completed by tests on small specimens for tensile, compressive and shear properties of the core and tensile properties of the face sheets. Table 1 gives an overview of the test programme including the failure modes. Table 2 lists the major mechanical and geometrical properties of the tested panels.

3.2 Test set-up

All test set-ups satisfied the requirements of EN 14509. For tests which are not part of EN 14509, such as two-span-tests, the test set-up adapted its principles. Figure 3 shows the test set-up for the two-span panel and simulated central support tests. One test set-up for the two span panel tests was slightly modified by changing the position of the load introduction to avoid shear failure (see also footnote 2 in table 1 for the consequence in failure mode). In all tests the deformation in span on both sides of the panel was measured (w_1 to w_4 respectively w_1 and w_2). The displacement transducer w_5 and w_6 recorded the indentation at the borders of the (simulated) mid support. For the simulated central support test the indentation was calculated out of the difference between the displacement of the hydraulic cylinder and the measured displacements w_1 , w_2 , w_5 and w_6 . For the two span panel tests only two line loads per span were applied to guarantee that the clear width between the mid support and the inner line loads is long enough to avoid a direct load transfer.

³ As discussed in section 2.3, EN 14509 does not directly define the required span length. But in tests for the CE markings for sandwich panels the examined panel would have been tested with 4900 mm or 5900 mm.

type of test	L in mm	test #	type of panel	L_S in mm	number of tests	1 st failure	2 nd failure
simulated central support test	5900	W_1	wall	60	3	a	–
		W_2		200	2	a	–
		R_1	roof	60	2	a	–
		R_2		200	2	a	–
simulated central support test	2500	W_3	wall	60	3	a/c ¹	–
		W_4		200	2	a	–
		R_3	roof	60	2	a/f ¹	–
		R_4		200	2	a	–
simulated central support test	1000	W_7	wall	60	3	d ¹	–
		W_8		200	3	a ¹	–
	1100	R_7	roof	60	3	d	–
		R_8		200	3	a	–
two-span test	2 x 2950	W_9	wall	60	3	d	2xb, 1xe ²
		W_10		200	3	b	–
		R_9	roof	60	3	d	e
		R_10		200	3	a ³	e ³
single-span test	5900	W_11	wall	–	1	a	–
		R_11	roof	–	2	a	–

¹ Failure mode not clearly classifiable.

² Slightly modified load distribution in this test.

³ Sequence of failure uncertain since the failures occurred one shortly after the other.

Failure a: Wrinkling at (simulated) mid support

Failure b: Shear failure at mid support

Failure c: Delamination of face sheet next to the (simulated) mid support (without kink)

Failure d: Compression failure of core (simulated) at mid support

Failure e: Wrinkling in span (only for two-span tests)

Failure f: Indentation at one side of the simulated mid support

Table 1: Overview of test programme and failure modes.

	E_{Ct} N/mm ²	E_{Cc} N/mm ²	G_C N/mm ²	f_{Ct} N/mm ²	f_{Cc} N/mm ²	f_{Cv} N/mm ²	σ_{w2} N/mm ²	t_1 mm	t_2 mm	$D d_C$ mm	e mm
wall	6,86	4,12	3,87	0,1620	0,1416	0,1650	182,6 ¹	0,49	0,46	78,8	76,9
roof	6,23	4,82	3,83	0,1588	0,1539	0,1588	209,0	0,48	0,39	79,4	88,3

¹ Wrinkling stress determined only out of one panel. The panel was slightly pre-damaged with local indentations. Failure occurred at one of the indentations.

Table 2: Mechanical and geometrical properties of tested panels (mean values). Notation according to EN 14509. Index 1 indicates the outer face sheet, index 2 the inner face sheet.

Figure 3: Test set-up. *Left:* Two-span panel test. *Right:* Simulated central support test.

4 TEST RESULTS

4.1 Determination of load at time of first failure

The load at time of first failure is the maximum applied load in the simulated central support tests. For two-span panel tests this load could not be clearly determined since neither the applied load nor the support reaction showed a sudden decrease at time of first failure. Actually, they both kept on increasing. So another measure was needed to determine the first failure load. The authors suggest to utilise the maximum sandwich moment M_S at mid support which is directly related to the compressive stress of the inner face sheet. For wall panels the sandwich moment equals the total moment. For roof panels the sandwich moment represents only a part of the total moment because of the inner static indeterminacy. According to the theory of profiled sandwich panels the bending moment of the profiled face sheet M_{F1} does not influence the stresses of the inner face sheet at mid support and is therefore not taken into account. In both cases, for wall and for roof panels, the system of figure 3 (left) is transferred to a system of a simply supported beam with span of two L and $R = R_1 + R_2$ acting as an external load (figure 4).

Figure 4: Static system to calculate M_S at mid support.

For wall panels M_S at mid support is directly gained out of the equilibrium conditions:

$$M(L) = M_S(L) = -0.25 \cdot (F + 2R) \cdot L \quad (3)$$

Since for roof panels the total moment $M(L)$ does not equal the sandwich moment $M_S(L)$, M_S is separated of the total moment using the sandwich theory for profiled face sheets. It can be either determined using a special sandwich programme or by superposition of the results of a single-span system with arbitrary point load, e.g. by equation (9.79) in [5].

Unfortunately, some of the roof panels for the two-span tests were pre-deformed due to storage conditions, compare figure 5. The gap between the support and the inner face of the panel varied between only a few millimetres up to a maximum of 40 mm. In consequence of this pre-deformation,

the static system changed in the first instance to a simply supported beam with a cantilever. With increasing deformation the gap vanished and the static system became the intended two-span beam. Although the ultimate load was not affected, this change in static system during the test significantly influenced the load of first failure. Hence, the sandwich moment was also calculated taking the two static systems into account. The point of transition from the simply supported beam with a cantilever to the two-span beam was defined as the kink in the F -over- R -curve. In theory R should equal F in the first system as indicated in figure 5. In the tests, the mid support force R never reached the exact value of F . Minor imperfections in the load positions and span lengths always exist. Additionally, for some tests the gap was not constant over the panel width so that the static system changed smoothly instead of all at once.

Figure 5: Pre-deformed panels for tests R_9_1, R_9_3, R_10_2 and R_10_3

Due to the difference between R and F , there are two possibilities to calculate the moment at mid support, from the left and from the right side:

$$M_{\text{left}} = -F/4 L + (F - R) L \quad (4)$$

$$M_{\text{right}} = -F/4 L \quad (5)$$

Considering the absolute values of the moments according to equation (4) and (5), it is obvious that M_{right} will always exceed M_{left} . If the difference remained under 15 %, the error could be treated as acceptable and the sandwich moment could be calculated from the right side. Otherwise the sandwich moment was calculated as well, but the quality of these results is doubtful. This is the case for R_9_1 and R_10_3. All results of these tests are put in parentheses.

4.2 Discussion of failure modes

The load bearing capacity of all panels consists of the applied load and the additional loads through the load introduction girders as well as the self-weight of the panels. The latter loads are not covered by the measured data, but they are included in all calculations with the help of the theory for thin faced and profiled sandwich panels. As explained in the previous section, the results of R_9_1 and R_10_3 may be doubtful. Additionally, W_10_3 was loaded unequally which resulted in a difference of load and deformation between one side and the other and a reduced maximum load. For this test the results are again parenthesised. The measuring of the mid support forces of W_9_1 showed some inconsistencies during the test by what a manual fitting became necessary.

Table 1 lists the failure modes of all tests. Not all panels failed in wrinkling which did not match the expectation. Some failure modes could not clearly be identified. This behaviour was especially observed for the smaller simulated central support tests with the smaller width of the load introduction beam. Nevertheless, the indicated failure modes are supposed to be correct since their determination included a careful examination of all measured data. Before looking at the wrinkling failure two other failure modes shall be discussed, the compressive and the shear failure of the core.

Two approaches to determine the support reaction capacity are given in equations (1) and (2). The corresponding action at time of failure is determined according to section 4.1. Table 3 lists the results. If one of the two equations for F_{R2} perfectly fitted, the utilisation would be 100 %. Equation (1) overestimates and equation (2) clearly underestimates the support reaction capacity. For all tests the

approach according to EN 14509, meaning equation (1), is not on the safe side. Except for one test (R_9_3) the safety concept would probably compensate the lack of safeness. Nevertheless, either the determination of compressive strength, or the approach of load distribution describe the real behaviour incorrectly. Using equation (2) instead, gives conservative results. It provides yet a good alternative, since this proof is normally not decisive in the total design. Test R_9_3 showed a very low mid support reaction. This was one of the tests, which transferred from a simply supported beam with a cantilever to a two-span beam. The gap measured about 40 mm. Maybe the unequal loading at the beginning resulted in a higher local pressure and as a consequence in an early failure. The two-span tests and the related simulated central support tests match well for the wall panels. For the roof panels R_9_2 correlates acceptably with the simulated central support tests. The change in static system might influenced the other two roof tests.

Simulated central support tests			Two-span panel tests		
test #	F / F_{R2} eq. (1)	F / F_{R2} eq. (2)	test #	R / F_{R2} eq. (1)	R / F_{R2} eq. (2)
W_7_1	89 %	146 %	W_9_1	83 %	136 %
W_7_2	89 %	146 %	W_9_2	80 %	131 %
W_7_3	88 %	144 %	W_9_3	86 %	140 %
R_7_1	83 %	144 %	R_9_1	(68 %)	(118 %)
R_7_2	84 %	146 %	R_9_2	73 %	126 %
R_7_3	83 %	145 %	R_9_3	51 %	88 %

Table 3: Tests with compression failure of core at (simulated) mid support: Ratio of support reaction to support reaction capacity. The ratios are calculated with the mean values of f_{C_c} without additional safety factors.

Table 2 provides the shear strength f_{C_v} for the tested elements. The load to calculate the maximum shear stress is the maximum load of the (simulated) central support, meaning the maximum applied load for the simulated central support tests and the maximum load at mid support for the two-span tests. Table 4 lists the results if the shear failure was decisive. Since the utilisation in shear is well below 100 %, none of the tests should have failed in such a way. The proof according to EN 14509 remains on the unsafe side again and is giving cause for concern because the SLS implies reduced safety factors additionally. Still there are only limited consequences for practical buildings as real conditions incorporate the combination of uniform and temperature loads, which result in a significant higher ratio of sandwich moment to mid support reaction. Thus, wrinkling as first failure mode becomes more likely. The fact that the related simulated central support tests failed in wrinkling or in compression of the core shows that the shear failure is close to disappear under conditions that are slightly changed. It is interesting to mention that an additional simulated support test, which was equal to the tests #8, but with half of the panel width, failed in shear.

Two-span panel tests		Two-span panel tests	
test #	τ / f_{C_v}	test #	τ / f_{C_v}
W_9_1	56%	W_10_1	69%
		W_10_2	71%
W_9_3	57%	W_10_3	(61 %)

Table 4: Tests with shear failure of core at (simulated) mid support: Ratio of shear stress to shear strength. The ratios are calculated with the mean values of f_{C_v} without additional safety factors.

The maximum sandwich moment at mid support was calculated according to section 4.1. Equation (6) shows how to determine the compressive stress out of the sandwich moment:

$$\max \sigma_2 = \max M_S / (e \cdot B \cdot t_2) \quad (6)$$

The maximum compressive stress of each test is related to the compressive stress for the simulated central support test according to EN 14509 ($L = 5900$ mm, $L_S = 60$ mm). Figure 6 refers these data to

the ratio of sandwich moment to (simulated) mid support reaction to show the relation to the span and to be able to present wall and roof panels in one single figure. It is not possible to directly compare the results for wall and roof panels because they are related to tests with different M_S/R -ratios. Table 5 shows the correlation between the span in tests and the corresponding ratio of sandwich moment and (simulated) mid support. Figure 6 does not include the tests R_9_1, R_9_3, R_10_2 and R_10_3 because there exist two M_S/R -ratios for the two static systems. The dashed lines in figure 6 indicate the relative wrinkling strength out of the six-point-bending tests (test #11). Table 2 lists the absolute values for the wrinkling strength. These lines are the upper limit for all other tests. It would have been possible to relate all tests to the corresponding wrinkling stress of tests #11 which would have made wall and roof panels directly comparable. This idea was dismissed since the wrinkling stress for the wall panels imports some uncertainty. It is based on only one test and the test panel was slightly pre-damaged.

Figure 6: Relative compressive strength of tested panels in dependence on the ratio of sandwich moment and (simulated) mid support reaction. One data point corresponds to one test. Numbers indicate the number of data points on top of each other if the difference is hardly visible. SCST: Simulated central support test. 2-SpT: Two-span panel test. 6-PBT: 6-point bending test.

		simulated central support test				two-span test	
	span	in mm	5900	2500	1100	1000	2950
wall	M_S / R	in mm	1475	625	–	250	256
roof	M_S / R	in mm	1240	450	130	–	139

Table 5: Correlation between span in test and ratio of sandwich moment to (simulated) mid support reaction.

Figure 6 shows that the wrinkling stress is strongly dependent on the M_S/R -ratio, which is directly related to the span in the simulated central support test. Since not all tests failed in wrinkling (compare table 1), some data points indicate only the lower limit for the wrinkling stress. Obviously, the support width positively influenced the wrinkling stress. The two-span tests and the related simulated central support tests failed with a similar relative compressive strength whereby the latter always result in slightly higher values. This difference turns to its maximum for the roof panels with $L_S = 200$ mm. 100 % in relative compressive strength indicate the exercised design concept on the basis of EN 14509. Higher values represent unused potential, lower values reduction in safety. As already

mentioned before, the tests with the lowest M_S/R -ratios (approx. $M_S/R \leq 400$ mm) do not represent real conditions. Although not usual in tests for CE markings, the simulated central support tests with a span of $L = 2500$ mm and a support width of $L_S = 60$ mm would have also satisfied the requirements of EN 14509 since the corresponding compressive strengths according to equation (2) were fulfilled.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

After a short review on existing simulated central support and two span tests, the design concept of EN 14509 at mid support was introduced. The minimum span length for the simulated central support tests and the proof of shear resistance were called into question. The span length results out of the questionable thought of EN 14509 to separate the failure modes. EN 14509 indirectly assumes that the first failure is equal to wrinkling failure at mid support and therefore allows the proof of shear resistance in the SLS.

To examine the quality of the design concept of EN 14509 a large test series was performed. The test series included tests for wall and roof panels, two support widths (60 and 200 mm), three different spans for simulated central support tests (1000/1100, 2500 and 5900 mm) and one span for the two-span panel tests (2 x 2950 mm). The ratio of sandwich moment to (simulated) mid support reaction corresponded between the two-span and the shortest simulated central support tests. For the two-span tests it was not possible to directly determine the load at time of first failure from the measured data. It was proposed to use the maximum sandwich moment instead which was calculated with the help of the measured mid support reaction. Some two-span tests required special treatment because they were pre-deformed in such a way that their static system was a simply supported beam with a cantilever at the beginning of the test.

The tests revealed some surprising results. Some of the panels with the lowest ratio of sandwich moment to (simulated) mid support did not fail in wrinkling, but in compression of the core or in shear. According to EN 14509 both failure modes should not have occurred. In fact, the test set-up for these tests has not represented real conditions, though the lack of safety in EN 14509 needs further revision. The examination of the wrinkling stresses showed that the simulated central support tests seem to be capable to replace the two-span tests, although they are slightly on the unsafe side. Wider support widths as well as larger spans in the simulated central support tests positively influenced the wrinkling stress. The comparison to the proceeding according to EN 14509 revealed conservative and again unsafe results. In summary, the design concept of EN 14509 provides resistances at mid support, which could not be confirmed in the experiment.

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